

International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research (IJEASR)

ISSN: 2349 -2899 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4808 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com>

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

AN UNDERSTANDING OF PSYCHOSOCIAL PROBLEMS AMONG ADOLESCENCE: BUILDING KNOWLEDGE AND GOOD PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

Adolescence is the most fascinating period in the life of an individual. Major biological and psychological developments occur during this phase of growth. It is the transitional stage of development between childhood and adulthood and it represents the period of time during which a person experiences a variety of biological changes and encounters a number of emotional issues. The word 'adolescence' is derived from the Latin word 'adolescere', which means to "to grow to maturity". It is the period of stress and strain. The ages which are considered to be part of adolescence vary by culture and ranges from pre teens to early twenties. It covers the period of life between ten and twenty years. In this period young people develop abstract thinking abilities, develop a clearer scene of psychological identity and increase their independence from parents. So many studies were carried out to analyse the psycho social problems among adolescents. Here the author tries to explain the various psychosocial issues of adolescence with the strong basis of various studies in India and abroad. The article highlights that a good understanding of the various concerns and issues of adolescents is required among the families. The author finally emphasized the significance of good practices and role of the multi-stakeholders for the developments of the adolescents.

Keywords: Adolescence, psycho social problems, development, multi-stakeholders, good practices

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is the period of physical and psychological development from the onset of puberty to maturity. It is also referred to as teenage years or youth. Adolescence is defined by World Health Organisation as the age group of 10-19 years. In India, adolescents (10-19 years) constitute 21.4 % of the population, comprising one fifth of the total population. Adolescence is the transitional stage of development between childhood and adulthood, representing the period of time during which a person experiences a variety of biological changes and encounters a number problems.

Adolescence can be a specifically turbulent as well as a dynamic period of one's life. It has been identified as a period in which young people develop abstract thinking abilities, become more aware of their sexuality, develop a clearer sense of psychological identity and increase their independence from parents. G. Stanley Hall denoted this period as one of "Storm and Stress" and, according to him, conflict at this developmental stage is normal and not unusual. Adolescents report that they are far happier spending time with similarly-aged peers as compared to adults. Consequently, conflict between adolescents and their parents increase at this time as adolescents strive to create a separation and sense of independence. Peer pressure is very prevalent during adolescence. Young

adolescents are particularly susceptible to conforming to the behavior of their peers. Adolescents are less likely to feel depressed or anxious if the peer group provides emotional support.

Adolescents are rich in memory, perceiving things, concept formation, association, generalization, imagination and decision making. Questioning on most of the things is prevalent but they become satisfied in approval and recognition of their own views. Adolescence is a period when rapid physiological changes and demands for new social roles take place. The adolescents, due to these changes often face a number of crises and dilemmas. Emotional development is at peak and there is no emotional stability in general. It is the period when the child moves from dependency to autonomy. It is a period demanding significant adjustment to the physical and social changes which distinguish childhood behavior from adult behavior. It is a period of rapid physical and psychological transition which makes adolescents particularly vulnerable to emotional conflicts and behavioral disorders.

Adolescents are facing multitude of problems throughout the world. Adolescents suffer from psychosocial problems at one time or the other during their development. The major psycho social problems are substance abuse, internalizing disorders (depression, anxiety) and externalizing disorders (delinquency, aggression, educational difficulties). Many of these problems are of transient nature and are often not noticed. Further children may exhibit these problems in one setting and not in other (e.g. home, school). Several key transitional periods (moving from early elementary to middle school, moving from middle school to high school or moving from high school to college) can present new challenges for these adolescents and symptoms of dysfunction may occur. Nowadays, because of rapid industrialization and urbanization majority of parents are employed and live in unitary setup, so unavoidably they get less time to look after their children. Under these circumstances, psychosocial (emotional and behavioral) problems and psychiatric problems are on the rise. Most of the epidemiological survey on school going children and adolescents has reported a wide variation (20-33%) in the prevalence of psychosocial problems.

There are several studies were highlighted the various psychosocial problems of adolescents.. A cross sectional study was conducted on prevalence of psychosocial problems among 840 adolescents in Dehradun. The results showed the overall prevalence of psychosocial problems to be 31.2%. Psychosocial problems were more in males (34.77) as compared to females (27.6%). Another study was conducted on prevalence of psycho social problems among 390 school going male adolescents. The study revealed that prevalence of the psychosocial problems was maximum 25.2% (14-15 yrs age group) and minimum 10.3% (10-13 yrs age group). The most common problem was educational difficulties found in 17.4% of the study population, followed by substance abuse (13.3%) and conduct disorders (9.2%).

National Crime Bureau's study discloses in 2005 out of 2555 adolescent suicide it was 1328 boys and 1227 girls. It also says that from the period 1967 to 1999 there is a 17.5% increase in the suicide. A recent study published, conducted on 11000 high school students' reveals that among the respondents 27 % has at least thought of suicide 16% planned suicide, 8% attempted suicide (Ahmad A, Khalique N, Khan Z, Amir A).

The major problem areas of most concern for high-risk adolescents are alcohol and drug abuse. It is difficult to draw the line between teens who are simply experimenting with alcohol and drugs and teens who have developed an alcohol or drug problem. Teens who begin using drugs early, who rely on alcohol and drugs to alleviate feelings of anxiety or depression ("self-medicate"), especially when such use is shared by their friends, may be at higher risk than other teens for developing a substance abuse problem. Parental substance abuse, including alcohol abuse, is a risk factor for the development of substance abuse problems for adolescents. 81% of high school students have tried alcohol; 32% had their first drink before the age of 13. Half of all high school students report having had more than one alcoholic beverage in the past 30 days, and approximately 30% report having had more than five alcoholic beverages at one time during this period. A desire to experiment and explore can manifest in a large of behavior – explore in sexual relationship, alcohol, tobacco and other substance abuse (Lee 2000, Jessor, R. (1991) et.al.

All of the ways adolescents develop—cognitively, physically, socially, emotionally—prepare them to Experiment with new behaviours as they transition from childhood to adulthood. This experimentation in turn helps them to fine-tune their development in these other realms. Risk taking in adolescence is an important way that adolescents shape their identities, try out their new decision-making skills, and develop realistic assessments of themselves, other people, and the world Such exploratory behaviours are natural in adolescence need room to experiment and to experience the results of their own decision making in many different situations. However, young people sometimes overestimate their capacities to handle new situations, and these behaviours can pose real threats to their health. To win the approval of peers or to avoid peer rejection, adolescents will sometimes take risks even they themselves judge to be “too risky” (*Jaffe, 1998, Ponton, 1997, hamburg, 1997*).

Adolescence is a developmental period in which the young person must negotiate fundamental psychosocial tasks in their development towards maturity and independence. The physical and psychological characteristics of adolescents and the nature of developmental tasks which they are expected to perform often pose certain challenges and problems for adjustment. Basically adolescents face problems related to their home, school and society. Self Related problems like – Anger, Hypersensitivity, Feeling of rebel, Personality etc....Home related problems like - Authoritative parenting, Poor rapport with parents, Lack of communication, Low socio-economic background etc...School related problems like - Not acceptable, Poor marks Too much homework, Gender bias, caste related problems, Generation gap, Orthodox practices ,Over expectations etc these are the common problems which adolescents face. The more serious problems include drug addiction, alcoholism, smoking etc. They may not appear in everybody. There are variations in the experience of these problems across people (*Obot, I. S., & Wagner, F. A. (2001)*).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

a).Psychological issues of adolescents:

An adolescent is a crucial phase in life and the presents of conditions like depression, anxiety and stress at this stage of life. Depression is characterized by more extreme feelings of hopelessness, sadness, isolation, worry, withdrawal and worthlessness that last for two weeks or more. The finding that 9 percent of high school students are severely depressed is important since depression is the most important risk factor for suicide. Depression in this population has been shown behaviour, homicidal ideation, tobacco use and other substance abuse into adulthood. The majority of suicides in India are by those below the age of 30 years. Anxiety is one of the most common psychological disorders in school-aged children and adolescents worldwide (*Costello, Mustillo, Erkanli, Keeler & Angold, 2003*). The prevalence rates range from 4.0% to 25.0%, with an average rate of 8.0% (*Bernstein & Borchardt, 1991; Boyd, Kostanski, 2000*).

Anxiety is associated with substantial negative effects on children’s social, emotional and academic success. Specific effects include poor social and coping skills, often leading to avoidance of social interactions, loneliness, low self-esteem, perceptions of social rejection, and difficulty forming friendships. Importantly, school avoidance, decreased problem-solving abilities, and lower academic achievement have also been noted as consequences (*Donovan & Spence, 2000; McLoone, Hudson & Rapee, 2006; Rapee, Kennedy, Ingram, Edwards & Sweeney, 2005*). In India, the main documented cause of anxiety among school children and adolescents is parents’ high educational expectations and pressure for academic achievement (*Deb, 2001*).

Stress is characterized by feelings of tension, frustration, worry, sadness and withdrawal that commonly last from a few hours to a few days Adolescents have stress, as they get confusing message ,have conflict with in family and school and have difficulties in establishing self – identify and self esteem. It is a time of increased thinking, emotionally and empathy. Personal adjustment problems and unhappy family environment may be factors of contributing depression. Stress and anxiety in adolescents are just as prevent as in adults .stressed out and negligent parent, abused or deprived childhood ,growing up tensions and demand for familial responsibility are the main cause of teens stress.

Stressed children's show signs of emotional disabilities, aggressive behaviour, shyness, social phobia otherwise often lack interest in otherwise enjoyable activities. Many teenagers tend to become nonconformists and fall prey to teenage depression in response to a variety of growing up anxieties. However stress induced fears and anxiety in children adversely affect children's performance at various levels (*M.K.C Nair*). Today stress levels among children have been going up dangerously due to the pressure of their academic or cultural activities. Not all children can cope with such high levels of expectation and parents do not seem to realize or accept that their children are under severe pressure (*Elizabeth Vadakkekara, 2003*). In a more informal survey of 60 young people (Walker, 1985), the primary sources of tension and trouble for teens and their friends were relationships with friends and family; the pressure of expectations from self and others pressure at school from teachers, grades and homework; financial pressures and tragedy in the lives of family and friends (described as death, divorce, cancer).

b). Psychological changes among adolescents:

a). Cognitive changes: Thinking begins between 11 and 15 . A sense of idealism the natural flower of abstract thinking. The adolescents become a misfit in such situations .Few significant differences have been identified in the cognitive changes of adolescent boys and girls; it appears that adolescent boys and girls do differ in their confidants in certain cognitive abilities and skills. Adolescent girls tend to feel more confident about their reading and social skills than boys and adolescent boys tend to feel more confident about their athletic and other activities. The adolescent becomes able to think in more abstract and logic terms. The quality of thinking in terms of grate ideals also emerges during the period.

b). Emotional changes: The physical and glandular changes of adolescents' produce emotional changes .The adolescent is exposed to new social situations, patterns of behaviour ,.and societal expectations which bring a sense of insecurity. It has been found that there is increase in the incidents of depression. The adolescents show the tendency of impulsive urge to take immediate action which often leads to risk taking behaviour.

c).Changes in attitude, interest and inter personal relationship: During adolescence there is a change in behavioural pattern, attitude and personality. Adolescents get themselves involved in political, ideological and social activities. Sometimes their involvement gives them an illusion of adulthood, power and importance. This inflated mood is often destructive. There may be a tendency to challenge parental ideology, authority, values etc. Adolescents may have a tendency to criticise and reform them .The relationship of the adolescents with the members of the family may sometimes become less cohesive because of their interests outside home .This results in enhancement of generation gap which is really the outcome of radical changes in the existing culture. In India this generation gap is much more in large families than in small families. Adolescents who are greatly educated and are exposed to grate social and cultural changes are found to be victims to generation gap. They may consider their parents old fashioned and outdated. They wish to spend more time outside their families than inside. It is difficult for them to adjust with the adults at home .They may turn rebellious. They like to spend more time with the peer groups and others who accept their interest, values and ideals.

Just as adults sometimes make poor decisions, so do adolescent. This can especially be a problem when poor decisions lead adolescents to engage in risky behaviours such as use of alcohol and violence. Immature adolescent are especially likely to choose less responsible opinions .This level of maturity of judgement has been found to be more important than age in predicting whether an adolescent will make more responsible decision (*Fischhoff , Crowell and Kipke ,1999*).The changes prepare them to experiment with new behaviours as they transition from childhood to adulthood. This experimentation in turns helps them to fine – tune their development in these other realms. Risk taking in adolescents is an important way that adolescents shape their identities, try out their new decision making skills and development realist assessment of themselves, other people and the world (*Ponton 1997*).The major problem areas of risk taking behaviour of adolescents are alcohol use, tobacco use, marijuana use, other illegal drug use, fighting, suicidal thoughts, weapon carrying, suicidal attempts, risky sexual activity etc.

Adolescent who begin using early, who rely on alcohol and drug to alleviate feelings of anxiety or depression, especially when such use is shared by their friends, may be at higher risk than other teens for developing a substance abuse problem. Parental substance abuse, including alcohol abuse is a risk factor for the development of substance abuse problems of adolescents (*Obot and Wagner, 2000*). The suicidal rate for adolescent represent approximately 12 % of the total mortality in this age group .Life time prevalence rates of suicide attempts among adolescents are reported to range from 3.0 – 7.1 % males suicide rate in this age group approximately 3 times higher in adolescent girls than among boys. poor problem solving capacity of the children due to limited exposure to real world may contribute to psychological factors of suicide, especially when they are faced with hard realities of life, such as trauma, abuse causing them fall prey of poor self esteem, helplessness, depression and gradually commit suicide. Lack of social support, especially of parents and relatives, violence at home and poor academic atmosphere, inadequate attention to their needs, over protection and over expectation of the parents may lead to suicide. The peer group influence, value systems, social networks of the adolescents may influence the act of suicide. There is an increasing rate of suicide among the adolescents of India during the exam season. Studies disclose that boys commit suicide 3 times more than girls (*De poul Times 2009*).

For some adolescents, risk taking behaviour may signal a problem that can threaten their well being on both the short term and long term. It is very important that the different between normal experimentation and signs of troubled or high risk youth (*American Psychological Association*).

3. SUPPORT SYSTEM

Adolescents is a period of great stress and strain .The adolescents are in need of discovering themselves and making proper use of their qualities and urges .They have to be guided in understanding the meaning of emotions and uncertainties , characteristic of the age. They may be victims of feeling of inferiority, guilt or fear. These will have to be avoided. They must be socialised so that they may become good and useful citizens. In these areas the family, peer group and teachers have significant roles to play.

a) Family: The influence of the family on the growing child is immense. For adolescents, For adolescents, family support is the most important element in their lives. As part of their growth experience, adolescents usually expect a lot of things from their parents. Inadequate support from the parents will likely increase the chance of getting depression among adolescents who get into unfortunate situation with their parents. This occurs because adolescent usually become confused when they expect to get plenty of help and positive reinforcement from their parents, but it does not happen (*Stice, Ragan, & Randall, 2004*).The parent tend to use reasoning and persuasion , explain rules ,discuss issues and listen respectfully. Adolescents who come from homes with this style of parenting tend to achieve more in school, report less depression and anxiety, score higher in measure of self reliance and self esteem and be less likely to engage in delinquent behaviour and drug abuse (*Carlson El Al 2000,Dorn Busch 1987*).

The level of parental supervision and monitoring necessary to promote healthy adolescent development can differ depending on the characteristics of the adolescent's peer and neighbourhood environment. Setting stricter limits may in fact be desirable for adolescents who live communities where there is a low level of adult monitoring, a high level of danger and higher level of problem behaviour among peers (*Roth and Brooks,2000*). Family closeness and attachment has reasonly been confirmed as the most important factor associated with not smoking , less use of alcohol and other drugs and fewer suicide attempts among adolescents(*Bearman and Blum,1997*).

b).Peer groups: Peer group has a significant role in the development of adolescents. At this stage, adolescents have a need to develop their social awareness and capacity for cooperation, adjustment, mutual trust, tolerance etc.This can be achieved affectively by their participation in groups consisting of their equals in age and experience i.e., peer groups. At the same time parents and teachers should guard them against participation in gangs. Gangs are formed for socially undesirable activities like smoking, alcoholism, use of drug etc.Organising youths for recreation. Sports, social work, religious

activities etc. Will provide them with the right and enriching social contact and avoid gang formation, the development of leadership qualities, loyalty, mutual respect, love of the weak etc are developed in peer activities (A.Antony).One of the most obvious change in adolescence is that the hub around which the adolescent's world revolves shifts from the family to the peer group .It is important to note that this decreased frequency of contact with family does not mean that family closeness has assumed less import ants for the adolescent (O'koon,1997).In order to establish a greater independence from their parents , adolescents must orient themselves toward their peers to a greater extend than they did in earlier stages of development. Peer group serve a number of important functions throughout adolescents, providing a temporary reference point for a developing sense of identity. Through identification with peers, adolescents begin to develop moral judgement and values and to define how they differ from their parents (Bishop and Inderbitzen,1995). Another important function of peer group is to provide adolescents source of information about the groups ,higher emphasis may be placed as peer groups throughout adolescents , particularly when they are in the minority in a school or community , as the group may provide a much needed sense of belonging within the majority culture (Sponsors and Dsorn busch, 1990).

Adolescent vary in the number of friends that they have and in how they spend time with their friends. Introverted youth tend to have fewer but closer relationships, and boys and girls differ with regard to the kinds of activities they engage in more action oriented pursuits, and girls spend more time talking together (Smith, 1997).

c).School: It is a prominent part of their life .It is here that they relate to and develop relationships with their peer and where they have the opportunity to develop key cognitive skills. For some youth, it is also a source of safety and stability. Teacher can influence the adolescents in earlier areas of development better than parents and friends , because they are better trained and equipped in organizing group activities , group discussion , study tours , project work ,sports and games to develop the spirit of cooperation , healthy competition ,tolerance ,leadership qualities etc .A good teacher can help the adolescents to learn the techniques of social living and adopt adult models. One of the need of adolescents is the choice of the vocation .Teachers can give proper guidance in this areas to help them select a vocations that is suitable for their aptitude and capacity. This is very important in the modern world where the students will have to make a choice among a number of vocations.perhaps the most important role of the teacher is to provide the adolescents with a model for imitation. An adolescent is a period of hero worship. If the teacher can attract the students by his personality, the students will not go after undesirable models of imitation (A. Antony).

4. MANAGEMENT OF ADOLESCENT PROBLEMS

The family and the school are the central places for the development of children. There are often gaps in this relationship, within the school, within the family, and in their relationships to each other and to the needs of students. This leads to so many psychological and social problems like anxiety,depression,mood disorders, stress and sometimes they become anti-social elements .In order to help the adolescent to overcome this problem their exist the need of counselling, life skill education and other sensitization programmes.

Growing into an adult a child makes us experience the problems in various domains such as:

- Personal
- Social
- Educational
- Vocational and career related

Through guidance and counselling services adolescents can be helped to solve these problems. With the help of career counselling and vocational guidance they can be helped with insights into the various career opportunities and educations choices personal and social counselling can help them in resolving their problems.

During the adolescent period ,they face lot of problems .life skill education helps the adolescents to improve their critical thinking, creative thinking, decision making, problem solving, self-awareness,empathy,effective communication, interpersonal relationship, coping with emotions and coping with stress. Life skills educations have been defined by the World Health Organization (WHO)

as “abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life”. They represent the psycho-social skills that determine valued behaviour and include reflective skills such as problem-solving and critical thinking, to personal skills such as self-awareness, and to interpersonal skills. Practicing life skills leads to qualities such as self-esteem, sociability and tolerance.

5. MULTI-STAKEHOLDERS: THE POSITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF ADOLESCENTS

The multiple stakeholders’ role and interactions with the adolescents are significant in influencing, supporting and creating an atmosphere of positive development among the targeted group. The effective interaction and support should be ideal to the adolescents and youth to their effectual growth and development. The following model illustrates that the Socio-ecological approaches are effective for solving problems that require comprehensive multi-factorial solutions (e.g. physical inactivity). These models address the interaction between individuals and multiple settings and levels of influence on behaviour and the interdependency between settings and levels⁹⁻¹². Using a socio-ecological framework (Figure 1), practitioners or researchers target one or more levels for change and develop relationships or broad partnerships across sectors and disciplines, necessary to facilitate the desired change.

Figure 1: Sociological model that highlights the multiple levels of influence: intrapersonal, interpersonal, organisational/environmental, community and policy levels and the interdependency between levels to achieve behaviour change and/or sustained uptake and utilisation of an innovation (ref 12).

6. GOOD PRACTICES AND DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES FOR THE ADOLESCENTS

Key elements to the Development of good practices and approaches among the adolescents are the following:

- Promotion and Practicing life Skills Education among adolescence and youth are viewed as a valued and respected asset to society;
- Policies and programs focus on the evolving developmental needs and tasks of adolescents, and involve youth as partners rather than clients;
- Families, schools and communities are engaged in developing environments that support youth;

- Adolescents are involved in activities that enhance their competence, connections, character, confidence and contribution to society;
- Adolescents are provided an opportunity to experiment in a safe environment and to develop positive social values and norms; and
- Adolescents are engaged in activities that promote self-understanding, self-worth, and a sense of belonging and resiliency.
- Genuine respect for youth and adult-youth relationships;
- The skills to empower young people to be involved in the decision-making process;
- Self-awareness and understanding of program goals, strategies and outcomes; and Conviction and belief that youth are capable and can contribute (*PositiveYouthDEV99*).

7. CONCLUSION

Adolescence is a crucial stage of life. From the above we can understand that so many studies were carried out to analyse the psycho social problems among adolescents. Researchers concentrated on the risk taking behaviour of adolescents and they analysed each and every aspect of their behaviour and provide guidelines for parents and teachers to support the adolescents to overcome the psycho social problems they faced. It is a great need to work with adolescents in any settings either schools, family, neighbourhood for better understanding of the changes experienced by them in different contexts. It is our responsibility to ensure that adolescents are adequately getting support from various stakeholders to cope up with issues, concerns and challenges faced them in the society and their relationships.

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